

CLASS OBSERVATION REFLECTION

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Abstract

This paper is a reflection of lesson observation. It is a comprehensive observation of a lesson on utube.com. It gives detailed information about the lesson and explains the actions taken. Personal views are also given in terms of student engagement, study atmosphere and selection of activities.

Class observation

1. I cannot explain how much I have learnt from observing the classroom when I reflect on my experiences in two different classrooms over the last week. The first lesson I observed was a full lesson video on utube.com (<https://youtu.be/mlrhVPdQuu0>), in which an EFL teacher Sarah Troughear teaches pre-intermediate class at the British Study Centres Oxford using Life coursebook series. The classroom environment was very smooth and pleasant with both all its cozy surroundings such as furniture, design and mutual interaction between the teacher and the students. Teacher doubles the comfort atmosphere with her kind character and warm manner of speech. The teacher is a real facilitator for learning by providing resources, encouraging students to be more active and monitoring their progress. It is a simple multicultural classroom with adult learners from different nations.

I was really impressed how the teacher connected all the activities. Although there is a main teaching coursebook “Life” pre-intermediate, teacher had prepared many various activities connecting them to the information in the book. Moreover, these

activities are not just do activities, they are really engaging. All activities were skill-based and in this class, particularly, reading and speaking skills were focused. In other words, the whole class was based on comprehensible input, interaction and output. Some activities were for taking input such as lead-in and reading task, while discussions and pairworks motivated students to interact with each other more in order to get more information for outcomes. The most meaningful part for me was when the teacher assigned the roles for the students and they gave their opinions as these individuals. They had to be in the shoes of other people and feel their life. I did not expect this kind of critical thinking assignment and that it had some continuation part as discussion. Having observed students' round table discussion, I realized that if they have their own responsibility, they try to do the task successfully.

Students were the central part of the lesson as the teacher gave some instructions to do and helped to ease their challenges if they have some while accomplishing the task. The teacher showed a role model in using scaffolding strategies for speaking. Having analysed this lesson, I learnt how to implement scaffolding in the classroom. Considering my previous concerns on understanding and using it, this part was relevant for me providing me with exact samples of scaffolding. I realized that the primary purpose of the scaffolding technique in education is to assist students in becoming self-sufficient in their task completion. Another important factor to consider is the effectiveness of the teachers' scaffolding method. To begin, teachers must be mindful of not dominating for assistance for an extended period of time, with the goal of allowing students to work independently. He/she tells pupils, based on the first stage of scaffolding, to just give a few clues to lead them to think and execute the assignment imaginatively. Teachers, on the other hand, may give hints as an initial performance when a student gets off track, then allow them to finish it. All these insights from the class will be useful for me in my future teaching actions.

I now feel ready to apply the knowledge of scaffolding in the classroom for speaking. In a future similar situation, I would use this kind of communicative activities in my class, as they are universal in content and purpose. I believe, if I use scaffolding in my classroom, my students will be happier as they have more opportunities for practice. Additionally, being a facilitator is not just to give directions, but it is guiding them into correct directions and supporting them with some knowledge, when they are needed.

References

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